

Technical report of the team Toofan2024

Seyed Alireza tabatabayy amir ali rahimi bardia kazemlou mohammad mehdi hashempour Seyed ali delbari mohammad taha babazadeh

ToofanTeam2024@gmail.com

Abstract. The Toofan team, newcomers to the competition scene. The game system they have adopted is a 4-3-3 formation, with rectangular midfielders and striker lines leading the attack, supported by left and right wingers (forwards). On the field, each player carefully considers the environmental conditions provided by the server and executes a programmed behavior accordingly. These behaviors include pressing, shooting towards the opponent's goal, dribbling, adjusting the game area, and passing. You can see the game system in picture 2-1-1.

Keywords: programming language, algorithm, simulation, robot, artificial intelligence.

Fig. 2-1-1.

1 Introduction

- 1.1 At the beginning of the game, each player will receive environmental information and make decisions based on the available functions in the game world. These decisions involve various actions such as dribbling, adjusting the game area, passing, and shooting when the player has possession of the ball. The effectiveness of these actions determines whether the player scores or loses possession of the ball, ultimately impacting their advantage in the game.

Fig. 2-2-1.

2 During attack times.

- 2.1 our game system consists of 2-2-1 formation, involving both the system and the players of our team.

3 Let's talk about the behaviors defined for when we have possession of the ball .

- 3.1 Passing

Pass to forward and winger

In this pass, when the ball is in the opponent's field and players 10, 9, and 11 are in distress or positioned on the edge, we pass the ball to them. To ensure accuracy, we utilize safe sectors to confirm the positions of these three players. The priority is given to player number 11, and we pass to them if they are available.

Pass to Front

This function selects the players who are in front of me and analyzes their positions using sectors to determine their proximity to the goal. Then, I pass the ball to them.

Safe pass

This pass is used when there is a teammate in any part of the field. The main goal is for the pass to reach its destination safely. The only difference with the usual pass is that the sector angles are wider than the rest of the passes.

Pass backward.

When the ball is in our own field, we only pass to players who are behind us. We confirm the safety of their positions using sectors and pay attention to their proximity to the goal. Then, we pass to one of them

3.2 Shooting

This shoot utilizes special artificial intelligence to predict multiple default paths. The AI then selects the best path to increase accuracy and avoid potential problems. If conditions make it impossible to score, a message is sent to the most deserving player to create the best scoring opportunity for the team.

3.3 Adapting the game area

This function evaluates all conditions to determine which side of the field is more advantageous - left or right. After selecting the preferred side, a message is sent to the players, specifying the formation needed to quickly move the ball to the identified side of the field.

3.4 . Behaviors when not in possession of the

ballPressing

The player identifies the closest opponent and initiates pressing. The player assesses the game environment to find the opponent nearest to them, calculates the distance, and begins pressing.

3.5 Conclusion

Teams that are new to this field face challenges in finding appropriate solutions and developing effective behaviors. Developing initial methods, testing, and evaluation contribute to more accurate behaviors over time. Implementing various game strategies and adapting tactics can be explored through continuous refinement.

3.6 Appreciation.

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